

NLR27999 can be planted as late as October without yield reduction. Both varieties yield better than local varieties, even when 60-d-old seedlings are planted. They have good tillering ability, and a high number of panicles/m², and grains/panicle. The 1,000-grain weight is similar and slightly less than that of local varieties (Table 1).

NLR9672-96 and NLR27999 were evaluated in replicated kharif varietal, multilocation, and minikit trials from 1981 to 1984. Check varieties were locally popular NLR9672 and NLR9674. The new rices yielded significantly more than the checks (Table 2). In 1983 trials at 5 sites,

Table 2. Performance of NLR9672-96 and NLR27999 at Nellore, India.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)						
	1981	1982	1983	1984	1983 (MLT)	1984 (MLT)	1984 (MT)
NLR27999	4.3	5.6	—	6.5	6.2	5.1	5.3
NLR9672-96	—	—	3.8	6.5	—	5.6	5.4
NLR9672	3.7	4.8	3.4	—	5.5	4.8	4.3
NLR9674	3.8	5.5	2.6	4.0	—	4.6	—
CD	0.23	0.25	0.19	0.35	—	0.38	—
CV%	4.0	3.24	15.0	11.24	—	16.08	—

^aMLT = multilocation trial, mean of 5 locations; MT = minikit trial, mean of 4 locations.

NLR27999 yielded an average 13% more than NLR9672. In 1984, NLR27999 yielded 6% more and NLR9672-96 17% more than NLR9672.

In minikit trials, NLR27999 yielded 23% more and NLR9672-96 25% more than NLR9672. The new varieties are becoming popular with farmers. *ℓ*

Abnormal spikelet on IR58

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IR58 developed 10-70% abnormal spikelets in the Jun-Sep 1984 crop in Isabela, Philippines. Incidence was highest in San Mateo, Kauayan, and Ramon municipalities. Spikelets remained open after flowering and had the following shapes: the tip of the palea and lemma bent inward; an extra lemma developed on the base outside the palea; there was no palea; the palea was malformed and the lemma was torn in two; the lemma had two awns and no palea (see figure). Flowering and ovary development seemed normal, but the

External shape of abnormal spikelet. Isabela, Philippines.

abnormal spikelets bore empty or tapering grains.

Transplanting began in late June. Days were cloudy and rain often fell before sunset. Day temperature was 30-33° C, and night temperature 27-30° C.

Lowest temperature was 25° C. Days were sunny when panicles began to form in mid-Aug.

No other varieties had abnormal spikelets. In 1985 dry season, few farmers planted IR58. *ℓ*

Reaction of rices to natural infection of leaf scald (LSc)

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LSc caused by *Rhynchosporium oryzae* is one of the most important wet season rice diseases in South Sulawesi. It caused serious losses on variety Bakka in 1976 in Gowa and Takalar districts and IR36 and IR50 in 1981-82 wet season at Maros Research Station.

Response of 10 cultivars to natural infection of LSc, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Variety	Score ^a
Bahagia	1
BR51-114-3-2-1	1
BR168-2B-23	1
BR189-103-2-1-4-2-1	1
CR1002	1
DV85	1
IR9101-37-1	1
IR92 17-58-2-2	1
IR15314-30-3-1-3	1
IR15429-268-1	1
IR8192-200-3-3-1-1 (resistant check)	3
IR36 (susceptible check)	8

^a1980 Standard evaluation system for rice 1-9 scale.

In 1983-84 we evaluated 100 cultivars for reaction to natural LSc infection under lowland conditions and 90-60-0 kg applied NPK/ha. Two rows of 10 plants of each test variety were planted at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Two rows of resistant IR8 192-200-3-3-1-1 and susceptible IR36 were planted after every 10 test varieties.

Forty-six varieties had some resistance. Ten varieties had resistance scores 1 to 3. Resistant check IR8192-200-3-3-1-1 scored 3 (see table). *ℓ*